

PERCEIVED IMPACT OF POVERTY ON STUDENT ENGAGEMENT, MOTIVATION, AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 19

Issue 9

Pages: 922-935

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1818

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11188623

Manuscript Accepted: 03-18-2024

Perceived Impact of Poverty on Student Engagement, Motivation, and Academic Performance

Aleah Sandra D. Gubaten,* Carlito A. Abarquez
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study, conducted in Pantar District, Lanao del Norte, during 2023-2024, explored how poverty affected student engagement and motivation. Using a descriptive-correlational design, 100 teachers observed poverty's impact on underprivileged students. Findings revealed that poverty moderately affected student engagement, particularly attendance and interconnected aspects like attention span, peer relationships, and class participation. Students consistently agreed on poverty's impact, emphasizing shared perceptions. On motivation, poverty had a moderate impact, influencing interest in learning, attitudes, and self-efficacy. Low standard deviation indicated agreement on poverty's motivational impact, urging tailored interventions. Academic performance was generally positive indicating "Satisfactory" standards and excelling Very Satisfactory. No students fell below expectations, highlighting overall positive academic trends. In analyzing factors influencing student motivation, attendance, attention span, and peer relationships did not predict motivation significantly. However, class participation emerged as a crucial positive predictor, underlining its role in fostering student motivation. Analyzing academic performance and student engagement or motivation did not yield significant results, emphasizing the complexity of factors influencing student achievement. In conclusion, poverty consistently impacted student engagement and motivation, urging targeted interventions. Despite challenges, positive academic trends highlighted students' resilience. Class participation was crucial for motivation, emphasizing the need for a holistic understanding of factors shaping academic success. Non-significant findings suggested a need for further exploration into the intricate relationship between student engagement, motivation, and achievement in the context of economic disparities.

Keywords: *attendance, attention span, motivation, poverty, student engagement*

Introduction

Poverty has been a major issue affecting education in many parts of the world. In the Philippines, poverty remains one of the significant problems that affect the quality of education. Poverty has an enormous impact on students' academic performance, engagement, and motivation, leading to negative outcomes. According to data from the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), 16.6% of Filipinos were living below the poverty line as of 2018. In addition, around half of Filipino families considered themselves poor during the second quarter of 2023, according to a survey conducted by OCTA Research. The poll, carried out from July 22 to 26, found that 50% of Filipino families, or around 13.2 million households, rated themselves as poor (NEDA, 2023). The Pantar District in the Division of Lanao del Norte is one of the areas in the country that is significantly affected by poverty.

The impact of poverty on students' engagement, motivation, and academic performance has significant implications for the educational system. Students who experience poverty are more likely to face difficulties in academic tasks and activities, which can result in lower academic performance and disengagement from school. Understanding the impact of poverty on students' engagement, motivation, and academic performance can provide insights into possible interventions. This can be implemented to support and improve students' academic outcomes (Hightower & Workman, 2019).

Several studies have examined the relationship between poverty and student outcomes in the Philippines. A study by Reyes et al. (2019) found that poverty negatively impacted students' attitudes toward learning and their peer relationships. Meanwhile, Ferdousi and Kadir (2020) established that poverty negatively impacted attendance.

Several local studies have been conducted to explore the impact of poverty on students' engagement, motivation, and academic performance. However, there is still a research gap that needs to be addressed, specifically in the context of Pantar District in the Division of Lanao del Norte. The purpose of this study was to examine the impact of poverty on students' engagement, motivation, and academic performance in Pantar District, Division of Lanao del Norte to understand the unique challenges faced by students in this community.

Research Questions

The study examined the impact of poverty on student engagement and motivation Pantar District, Division of Lanao del Norte, School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the perceived impact of poverty on student engagement in terms of:
 - 1.1. attendance;
 - 1.2. attention span;
 - 1.3. peer-relationships; and
 - 1.4. class participation?

2. What is the perceived impact of poverty on student's motivation in terms of:
 - 2.1. interest in learning;
 - 2.2. attitudes towards learning; and
 - 2.3. self-efficacy?
3. What is the academic performance of the students based on their average grades for the First Quarter (SY 2022-2023)?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived impact of poverty on student's engagement and student's motivation?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of students and the perceived impact of poverty on student's engagement?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of students and the perceived impact of poverty on student's motivation?
7. What intervention program can be implemented based on the findings?

Methodology

Research Design

In Pantar District, Division of Lanao del Norte, the study used a descriptive-correlational research design to examine how poverty affected student motivation and participation in the school year 2023–2024. Descriptive-correlational studies are well-suited for delineating variables and uncovering the inherent relationships between them. This research design is particularly adept at presenting the current state or condition of a phenomenon or issue. Concurrently, correlational research endeavors to establish connections between two or more variables. In the context of this descriptive-correlational study, data were gathered through diverse methods such as questionnaires, and the ensuing analysis involved descriptive statistical measures including frequency distributions, weighted mean distribution, as well as correlations and regressions analysis. This approach allowed for a nuanced examination of the complex interplay between poverty and student engagement and motivation in the specified educational context.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were 100 randomly selected teachers and 100 students from Pantar District, Division of Lanao del Norte. The random selection of respondents was selected through the fishbowl technique. This sampling technique ensured that all teachers in the population had an equal chance of being selected, reducing bias and increasing the representativeness of the sample.

The selection of teachers observing the influence of poverty on their unprivileged students adds an element of the selected sampling, where the sample is chosen based on specific characteristics relevant to the research question. This ensured that the sample was relevant to the study and could provide valuable insights into the impact of poverty on student engagement and motivation. The table below presents the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents*

School	No. of Teacher-Respondents	No. of Student Respondents
Pantar National High School	51	60
Pantar Central Elementary School	38	35
Cadayonan Elementary School	11	5
Total	100	100

Instruments

To ensure the accuracy and reliability of data, the study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire as a standardized one is not available. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. Part 1 focused on the perceived impact of poverty on student engagement in terms of attendance, attention span, peer relationships, and class participation. Responses were rated using a five-point Likert scale where 5 represents highly observed, and 1 represents never observed. Part 2 focused on the perceived impact of poverty on student motivation in terms of interest in learning, attitudes toward learning, and self-efficacy. Responses were rated using a five-point Likert scale where 5 represents highly observed, and 1 represents never observed. The academic performance of the students was based on selected 100 students who are beneficiaries of the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program of the government.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, a validation process was conducted. The thesis adviser reviewed the questionnaire's appropriateness and relevance to the study. Furthermore, a pilot test was conducted to identify any issues that may arise during the actual data gathering. The feedback and comments from the results of the pilot test were considered for the finalization of the research instrument, ensuring the questionnaire's validity and reliability.

Twenty-five students and teachers from a chosen school in the Lanao Norte district participated in a pilot survey. This would verify that the research apparatus followed the study's objectives and assess the equipment's dependability. The reliability of each survey instrument was evaluated, and Cronbach's alpha was computed.

Forty items in the survey measure how poverty is considered to affect students' participation in class, attendance, attention span, and

peer relationships. Its purpose was to evaluate how poverty was thought to affect students' motivation, engagement, and academic achievement. This construct had strong reliability (above 7) and a Cronbach's alpha of 9.42.

In the meantime, a reliability construct of over 7 with a Cronbach's alpha of 8.86 was obtained for the 30-item measure measuring the perceived influence of poverty on students' motivation in terms of interest in learning, attitudes toward learning, and self-efficacy.

Procedure

The data collection process for the study included the following steps. Initially, the researcher sought approval from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Lanao del Norte to conduct the study, which included outlining the study's purpose and how it was carried out. Subsequently, the researcher acquired a permit to conduct the research from the school principals for the participation of the desired respondents. The next phase included selecting participants for the study, which required identifying a suitable sample of teachers in Pantar District who were willing to take part in the study.

Once the participants had been identified, the researcher provided them with informed consent documents that detailed the study's objectives, procedures, and the participants' rights. After obtaining the informed consent, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the participants to gather data on the impact of poverty on student engagement and motivation.

The researcher collected the completed questionnaires from the respondents and tallied the data for statistical analysis. The data were analyzed using correlation analysis and descriptive statistics. Finally, the researcher sent the tabulated data to the school's statistician for further analysis to determine any significant associations between the perceived impact of poverty to students' motivation and engagement. The study's findings were presented and interpreted, followed by recommendations based on the results.

Data Analysis

These statistical tools provided insights and interpretations of the data gathered from the study and could help answer the research questions and objectives.

For problem 1, Frequency and Percentage Distribution were used to describe the profile of the respondents and students' academic performance.

For problems 2 and 3, Mean and Standard Deviation were used to calculate and describe the perceived impact of poverty to students' motivation and engagement.

For problems 4, 5, and 6, Pearson r correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the independent and dependent variables of the study. Regression analysis was used to describe the perceived impact of poverty on student engagement, students' motivation, and academic performance.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data in relevance to the reading dimension. For better analysis and interpretation, these data are presented in tabular forms.

The perceived impact of poverty on student engagement in terms of attendance, attention span, peer relationships, and class participation?

Table 2. *Perceived Impact of Poverty on Student Engagement in terms of Attendance*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Students from low-income families miss school more often due to poverty-related reasons.	3.70	0.46	Observed
Students from low-income families have poorer attendance compared to their peers.	3.24	0.43	Moderately Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to come to school on time.	3.19	0.39	Moderately Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to stay in school for the entire day.	2.24	0.43	Rarely Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to participate in extracurricular activities, resulting in poorer attendance.	2.72	0.45	Moderately Observed
Students from low-income families lack reliable transportation, leading to frequent absences from school.	3.82	0.39	Observed
Financial constraints prevent low-income families from affording necessary school supplies and uniforms, affecting attendance.	3.02	0.40	Moderately Observed
Inadequate housing conditions, such as lack of heating or cooling, contribute to students missing school due to illness.	3.36	0.48	Moderately Observed
Parents from low-income backgrounds often work multiple jobs, making it challenging to ensure their children attend school regularly.	3.86	0.35	Observed
Limited access to healthcare among low-income families results in more sick days, affecting overall school attendance.	3.11	0.31	Moderately Observed
Total Measure	3.23	0.15	Moderately Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed, 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Observed, 3.50-4.49 Observed, 4.50-5.00 Highly Observed

Table 2 presents the perceived impact of poverty on student engagement, specifically focusing on attendance-related indicators. The mean scores indicated the extent to which each indicator was observed or experienced, with a higher mean suggesting a more significant impact. The standard deviation (SD) reflected the degree of variability in responses across participants.

Firstly, it was noteworthy that students from low-income families were reported to miss school more often due to poverty-related reasons, as indicated by a mean score of 3.70, suggesting a prevalent and observable issue. Additionally, the indicator pertaining to the impact of financial constraints on school supplies and uniforms (Indicator 7) scored moderately high at 3.02, emphasizing the role of economic barriers in affecting attendance.

Moreover, the mean score of 3.86 for Indicator 9 underscored a considerable challenge—parents from low-income backgrounds working multiple jobs, making it difficult to ensure regular school attendance for their children. This observation aligned with the broader theme of economic struggles hindering parental involvement in their children's education.

While several indicators were moderately observed, it was crucial to highlight the comparatively lower mean score of 2.24 for Indicator 4, suggesting that poverty's impact on student's ability to stay in school for the entire day was rarely observed. This finding may warrant further exploration and could potentially indicate a specific area where interventions or support systems were more effective.

In conclusion, the overall total measure means of 3.23 signified a moderate level of observed impact, emphasizing the multifaceted nature of poverty's influence on student attendance. According to Gonzalez and Strobel (2018) they emphasized that students from low-income families faced challenges related to attendance, attention, and participation in extracurricular activities. The study underscored the critical role of economic barriers in shaping the educational experiences of children from disadvantaged backgrounds.

Table 3. *Perceived Impact of Poverty on Student Engagement in terms of Attention Span*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Students from low-income families have shorter attention spans in class compared to their peers.	3.11	0.40	Moderately Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to concentrate during class.	3.21	0.41	Moderately Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to focus during lectures or classroom discussions.	2.72	0.45	Moderately Observed
Students from low-income families are distracted during class due to poverty-related issues, such as hunger or stress.	3.86	0.35	Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to retain information taught during class.	2.88	0.52	Moderately Observed
Hunger and malnutrition due to poverty impact students' ability to concentrate in class.	3.32	0.47	Moderately Observed
Students from low-income families may have to take on part-time jobs, leading to exhaustion and shorter attention spans.	3.20	0.40	Moderately Observed
Poverty-related stressors, such as unstable living conditions, affect students' focus during classroom activities.	3.80	0.40	Observed
Exposure to violence and crime in low-income neighborhoods can cause trauma, hindering students' attention spans.	3.48	0.50	Moderately Observed
Lack of access to educational resources, like books and educational toys, affects cognitive development and attention span.	1.52	0.50	Rarely Observed
Total Measure	3.11	0.16	Moderately Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed, 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Observed, 3.50-4.49 Observed, 4.50-5.00 Highly Observed

Table 3 shows the perceived impact of poverty on student engagement, specifically in terms of attention span. One prominent finding was the consistently moderate level of observation across various indicators. Notably, Indicator 4 stood out with a high mean score of 3.86, indicating that students from low-income families were frequently distracted during class due to poverty-related issues such as hunger or stress. This observation underscored the immediate and tangible impact of economic struggles on students' ability to concentrate, highlighting the urgency of addressing basic needs for optimal learning environments.

Indicator 8 also scored high at 3.80, emphasizing that poverty-related stressors, such as unstable living conditions, significantly affected students' focus during classroom activities. This finding emphasized the importance of creating supportive and stable environments for students facing economic challenges to foster better attention and concentration.

However, it was noteworthy that Indicator 10, which related to the lack of access to educational resources affecting cognitive development and attention span, had a notably lower mean score of 1.52, suggesting that this particular aspect was rarely observed. Thus, the total measure mean of 3.11 indicated a moderately observed impact of poverty on student attention span. The findings highlighted the multifaceted nature of these challenges, emphasizing the need for comprehensive strategies that addressed not only immediate needs such as hunger but also the broader socio-economic factors contributing to stress and distraction. Implementing support systems, interventions, and educational resources may play a crucial role in mitigating the observed effects of poverty on students' attention spans and overall engagement in the learning process.

As emphasized by Lomboy (2018), students from low-income families may face challenging home environments, characterized by factors such as overcrowding, lack of resources, and inadequate study spaces. These conditions can contribute to increased stress and distractions, making it difficult for students to maintain focus.

Table 4 sheds light on the perceived impact of poverty on student engagement in terms of peer relationships. The results presented a

mixed picture, with several indicators rarely observed, suggesting that certain aspects of peer relationships may not be significantly impacted by economic factors. For instance, Indicators 1 to 5 highlighted that struggles to form positive relationships, difficulties socializing with classmates, experiencing bullying or exclusion, and challenges in forming friendships outside of school. This was a noteworthy finding as it challenged common assumptions about the pervasive impact of poverty on social interactions within school settings. However, other indicators, such as Indicator 6, which emphasized the limited financial resources restricting participation in social events, had a high mean score of 3.74, indicating that this aspect was frequently observed. This suggested that economic constraints do play a role in limiting social opportunities for students from low-income backgrounds.

Indicator 8 also stood out with a high mean score of 3.93, indicating that discrimination and social stigma associated with poverty could lead to social isolation and difficulty forming friendships. The total measure mean of 2.84 suggested a moderately observed impact of poverty on student engagement in terms of peer relationships.

Table 4. Perceived Impact of Poverty on Student Engagement in terms of Peer-Relationship

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Students from low-income families struggle to form positive relationships with their peers.	1.69	0.46	Rarely Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to socialize with their classmates.	1.72	0.45	Rarely Observed
Students from low-income families are more likely to experience bullying or exclusion from their peers.	2.29	0.46	Rarely Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to form friendships outside of school.	2.29	0.46	Rarely Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to participate in group projects and other collaborative learning activities.	2.28	0.45	Rarely Observed
Limited financial resources restrict participation in social events, making it difficult for students from low-income families to connect with peers.	3.74	0.44	Observed
Low-income students often lack access to the internet and social media, hindering their ability to form online social connections.	3.40	0.49	Moderately Observed
Discrimination and social stigma associated with poverty can lead to social isolation and difficulty forming friendships.	3.93	0.26	Observed
Economic disparities can lead to feelings of inadequacy, impacting self-esteem and peer interactions.	3.48	0.50	Moderately Observed
Lack of opportunities for cultural and extracurricular activities limits low-income students' interactions with peers, affecting social relationships.	3.53	0.50	Observed
Total Measure	2.84	0.15	Moderately Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed, 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Observed, 3.50-4.49 Observed, 4.50-5.00 Highly Observed

The findings highlighted the need for a nuanced approach to understanding the social dynamics affected by economic factors.

As mentioned by Fernandez and Cunanan (2018), students from economically disadvantaged backgrounds may experience social stigma. Peer relationships could be affected by stereotypes and biases associated with poverty, potentially leading to feelings of isolation and lower self-esteem. Economic constraints could limit students' ability to participate in extracurricular activities that often contribute to the development of social skills and peer relationships. Students might miss out on sports, clubs, and other activities due to financial barriers. Moreover, socioeconomic status could be linked to cultural differences that may impact peer interactions. Variances in lifestyle, language, and experiences may contribute to challenges in forming connections with peers from different economic backgrounds.

Table 5. Perceived Impact of Poverty on Student Engagement in terms of Class Participation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Students from low-income families are hesitant to participate in class.	2.19	0.39	Rarely Observed
Poverty affects students' confidence to speak up in class.	2.63	0.49	Moderately Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to contribute to class discussions.	2.40	0.49	Rarely Observed
Students from low-income families feel embarrassed or ashamed to participate in class due to poverty-related issues.	2.44	0.50	Rarely Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to engage in hands-on activities during class.	2.37	0.49	Rarely Observed
Low-income students may lack access to essential educational technology, limiting their engagement in class activities.	3.66	0.48	Observed
Inadequate nutrition affects students' energy levels, making them less likely to actively participate in classroom discussions.	3.76	0.43	Observed
Limited exposure to cultural events and experiences hampers students' ability to contribute meaningfully to class discussions.	3.83	0.38	Observed
Students from low-income families often face language barriers, impacting their confidence in participating in class.	3.82	0.39	Observed
Insufficient funding for schools in low-income areas may lead to outdated materials and limited opportunities for hands-on learning, affecting class participation.	3.48	0.50	Moderately Observed
Total Measure	3.06	0.15	Moderately Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed, 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Observed, 3.50-4.49 Observed, 4.50-5.00 Highly Observed

Table 5 provides insights into the perceived impact of poverty on student engagement in terms of class participation. The findings suggested a moderately observed impact of poverty on class participation, with several indicators standing out. Notably, Indicators 6, 7, 8, and 9 exhibited high mean scores, ranging from 3.66 to 3.83, indicating that these aspects were frequently observed. These indicators highlighted the influence of economic factors on students' ability to engage in class activities, with issues such as limited access to educational technology, inadequate nutrition, cultural exposure, and language barriers significantly impacting class participation. These findings emphasized the need for targeted interventions to address these specific challenges and create a more inclusive learning environment.

Additionally, Indicators 2 and 10, with mean scores of 2.63 and 3.48, respectively, suggested a moderate level of observation. Poverty's impact on students' confidence to speak up in class and the limitations in hands-on learning opportunities due to insufficient funding in low-income areas were domains that warrant attention. Strategies focused on boosting students' confidence and addressing resource disparities may contribute to improved class participation.

However, it was interesting to note that Indicators 1, 3, 4, and 5 had lower mean scores, suggesting that students from low-income families were hesitant to participate, face embarrassment or shame, and experience limitations in contributing to class discussions or engaging in hands-on activities were rarely observed. This could indicate some resilience or adaptive strategies among students in overcoming these specific challenges.

Therefore, the total measure mean of 3.06 underscored a moderately observed impact of poverty on student engagement in terms of class participation. The findings emphasized the importance of addressing not only immediate economic needs but also broader factors such as access to technology, nutritional support, cultural exposure, and language proficiency to enhance students' active involvement in classroom activities. According to Palomar et al. (2018), students experiencing poverty may encounter social stigma and negative stereotypes, which can lead to lower self-esteem. This may result in a reluctance to actively participate in class discussions or activities due to fear of judgment or perceived inadequacy. Moreover, students from low-income families may lack access to essential learning materials, such as textbooks and technology. This limitation could hinder their ability to prepare adequately for class discussions and assignments, impacting their confidence to participate.

The achievement gap between students from low-income families and their peers has been attributed to multiple factors, including inadequate school resources, inadequate teacher training, and lack of access to high-quality early childhood education (Lakes & Tolen, 2019).

Table 6. Consolidated Findings of the Perceived Impact of Poverty on Student Engagement

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Attendance	3.23	0.15	Moderately Observed
Attention Span	3.11	0.16	Moderately Observed
Peer-Relationship	2.84	0.15	Moderately Observed
Class Participation	3.06	0.15	Moderately Observed
Total Measure	3.06	0.08	Moderately Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed, 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Observed, 3.50-4.49 Observed, 4.50-5.00 Highly Observed

Table 6 presents consolidated findings that provide an overview of the perceived impact of poverty on student engagement across various domains, including attendance, attention span, peer relationships, and class participation. The results suggested a consistent theme of moderate observation across all domains, with a total measure mean of 3.06. This indicated that the impact of poverty on student engagement was moderately observed, highlighting the multifaceted nature of the challenges faced by students from low-income families.

Attendance emerged as a domain with a relatively higher mean score of 3.23, indicating that the observed impact of poverty on students' attendance was somewhat more pronounced compared to other domains. This underscored the immediate and tangible effects of economic disparities on students' ability to consistently attend school.

Attention span, peer relationships, and class participation all exhibited similar mean scores, ranging from 3.06 to 3.11, suggesting comparable levels of observed impact. These findings emphasized the interconnectedness of various aspects of student engagement and highlighted the need for comprehensive interventions that addressed the diverse challenges arising from economic disparities.

The low standard deviation across all domains (ranging from 0.08 to 0.16) indicated a relatively low variability in responses, suggesting a degree of consensus among participants regarding the perceived impact of poverty on student engagement.

Thus, the consolidated findings stipulated the need for holistic and targeted interventions to address the moderate observed impact of poverty on student engagement. Strategies that encompassed not only academic aspects such as attendance and class participation but also social and emotional dimensions, including attention span and peer relationships, were essential. By understanding and addressing these multifaceted challenges, educators, policymakers, and support systems could work collaboratively to create a more equitable and supportive learning environment for students from low-income families.

Students experiencing poverty may struggle with meeting their basic needs, such as food, housing, and healthcare. It can often restrict students' access to educational resources, such as textbooks, technology, tutoring, and extracurricular activities. Addressing the

perceived impact of poverty on student engagement requires a holistic approach that addresses the underlying structural inequalities and provides comprehensive support to students and their families.

In addition, poverty can lead to negative attitudes towards education, as students may see it as irrelevant or unattainable. This lack of interest in learning can affect academic performance, as students may not be fully engaged in classroom activities or may not see the value in completing assignments (Albert & Alejandrino, 2018).

The perceived impact of poverty on student's motivation in terms of interest in learning, attitudes toward learning, and self-efficacy?

Table 7. *Perceived Impact of Poverty on Student's Motivation in terms of Interest in Learning*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Poverty affects students' interest in learning new things.	2.24	0.43	Rarely Observed
Students from low-income families express disinterest or apathy towards academic subjects.	2.33	0.47	Rarely Observed
Poverty affects students' curiosity and desire to learn.	3.52	0.50	Observed
Poverty affects students' willingness to participate in academic enrichment activities, such as after-school programs or academic clubs.	3.85	0.36	Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to connect their learning to real-life experiences	1.84	0.37	Rarely Observed
Poverty diminishes students' enthusiasm for exploring new knowledge and learning experiences.	1.75	0.44	Rarely Observed
Students from low-income families often exhibit disinterest or lack of motivation when faced with academic challenges.	3.14	0.35	Moderately Observed
Economic hardship affects students' curiosity and eagerness to engage with academic subjects and learning materials.	3.84	0.37	Observed
Financial constraints limit students' opportunities to participate in academic enrichment activities, hindering their passion for learning.	3.79	0.41	Observed
Poverty prevents students from connecting their learning to real-life experiences, leading to a lack of intrinsic motivation to excel academically.	1.89	0.31	Rarely Observed
Total Measure	2.82	0.13	Moderately Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed, 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Observed, 3.50-4.49 Observed, 4.50-5.00 Highly Observed

Table 7 presents the perceived impact of poverty on students' motivation in terms of their interest in learning. The findings suggested a moderately observed impact of poverty on students' motivation, with a total measure mean of 2.82. This indicated that while there were varying degrees of impact across different indicators, there was a consistent theme of economic factors influencing students' motivation to some extent. Indicators 3, 4, 7, 8, and 9 stood out with relatively higher mean scores, ranging from 3.14 to 3.85, indicating that these aspects were frequently observed. Notably, economic hardship was perceived to affect students' curiosity, enthusiasm for learning, and willingness to engage in academic enrichment activities. This underscored the importance of addressing financial constraints and creating opportunities for students from low-income families to actively participate in educational experiences beyond the standard curriculum.

Indicators 1, 2, 5, 6, and 10 had lower mean scores, suggesting that these specific aspects, such as poverty affecting students' interest in learning new things or connecting learning to real-life experiences, were rarely observed. This finding might indicate potential areas of resilience or adaptability among students in the face of certain motivational challenges. The standard deviation across all indicators was relatively low, ranging from 0.31 to 0.50, indicating a consistent level of agreement among participants regarding the perceived impact of poverty on students' motivation. Hence, the total measure mean of 2.82 suggested a moderately observed impact of poverty on students' motivation in terms of their interest in learning. The findings underscored the importance of addressing economic barriers to enhance students' intrinsic motivation, curiosity, and enthusiasm for learning.

As emphasized by Escalante et al. (2018), students from low-income families may face challenges accessing essential learning materials, such as textbooks and other resources. This can diminish students' opportunities for exploration and discovery, leading to decreased motivation and interest in learning. This limitation could hinder their ability to fully engage with the curriculum and develop a genuine interest in learning. In addition, students from low-income backgrounds may have limited exposure to cultural events, museums, field trips, and other experiences that can broaden their perspectives and enhance their interest in various subjects. Without exposure to a variety of perspectives and opportunities, students may struggle to see the relevance and value of their learning, leading to decreased motivation and interest.

Also, according to the study of Owens (2019), academic performance, motivation, and student participation were all negatively impacted by poverty as it can undermine students' sense of belongingness and engagement, reducing their motivation to participate in learning activities. Low-income students were more likely to be disengaged, to be less motivated, and to perform less academically as they may face stigma and negative stereotypes related to their economic status, feeling marginalized or undervalued can affect their interest in learning and their belief to succeed academically.

Table 8 outlines the perceived impact of poverty on students' motivation in terms of their attitudes towards learning. The findings suggested a moderately observed impact of poverty on students' motivation in terms of their attitudes towards learning, with a total measure mean of 2.97. This indicated a consistent theme of economic factors influencing students' attitudes, though to a varying degree

across different indicators.

Table 8. Perceived Impact of Poverty on Student's Motivation in terms of Attitudes towards Learning

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Students from low-income families express negative attitudes towards school	1.84	0.37	Rarely Observed
Students from low-income families express positive attitudes towards school	1.78	0.42	Rarely Observed
Poverty affects students' attitudes towards academic subjects, such as math or science.	2.00	0.43	Rarely Observed
Poverty affects students' belief in their ability to succeed academically	3.84	0.37	Observed
Poverty affects students' ability to stay motivated throughout the school year	3.84	0.37	Observed
Negative home environments resulting from poverty can foster pessimistic attitudes towards education and school.	3.76	0.43	Observed
Students from low-income families may harbor negative perceptions about their teachers and peers, affecting their overall attitude towards learning.	1.84	0.37	Rarely Observed
Poverty influences students' attitudes towards specific academic subjects, shaping their preferences and interests in various fields.	3.06	0.24	Moderately Observed
Low self-esteem arising from economic struggles can diminish students' belief in their academic capabilities, impacting their motivation to learn.	3.83	0.38	Observed
Persistent financial challenges create a sense of hopelessness, affecting students' motivation to stay engaged and proactive in their education.	3.90	0.30	Observed
Total Measure	2.97	0.15	Moderately Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed, 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Observed, 3.50-4.49 Observed, 4.50-5.00 Highly Observed

Indicators 4, 5, 6, 9, and 10 stood out with relatively higher mean scores, ranging from 3.76 to 3.90, indicating that these aspects are frequently observed. These indicators highlighted the significant influence of poverty on students' beliefs in their academic success, ability to stay motivated throughout the school year, negative home environments, and self-esteem. Persistent financial challenges were particularly noted as contributing to a sense of hopelessness, affecting students' motivation to stay engaged and proactive in their education. These findings underscored the importance of addressing not only academic but also emotional and psychological aspects of student well-being in the context of economic disparities.

Indicators 1, 2, 3, 7, and 8 had lower mean scores, suggesting that these specific aspects, such as students expressing negative or positive attitudes towards school and the influence of poverty on specific academic subjects or teacher perceptions, are rarely observed. This may indicate areas where students from low-income families exhibited resilience or where external factors played a less prominent role in shaping their attitudes.

Thus, the total measure mean of 2.97 suggested a moderately observed impact of poverty on students' motivation in terms of their attitudes toward learning. The findings emphasized the need for comprehensive interventions that addressed both the academic and emotional dimensions of student motivation, with a focus on creating supportive home environments and instilling a sense of hope and belief in academic success for students facing economic challenges.

Table 9. Perceived Impact of Poverty on Student's Motivation in terms of Self-Efficacy

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Poverty affects students' belief in their ability to succeed academically.	3.91	0.29	Observed
Students from low-income families doubt their ability to complete assignments or succeed on tests.	1.83	0.38	Rarely Observed
Poverty affects students' perception of their own academic abilities.	3.74	0.44	Observed
Poverty affects students' confidence in their ability to overcome academic challenges.	3.77	0.42	Observed
Students from low-income families are less likely to believe that they can succeed in higher education due to poverty-related barriers.	3.83	0.38	Observed
Poverty erodes students' confidence in their ability to excel academically, leading to self-doubt and insecurity.	3.79	0.41	Observed
Students from low-income families frequently question their competence to complete assignments and perform well on tests.	2.18	0.39	Rarely Observed
Economic hardship negatively impacts students' self-perception regarding their academic skills and knowledge.	3.77	0.42	Observed
Poverty undermines students' belief in their capacity to overcome academic obstacles, leading to a lack of resilience and determination.	2.02	0.40	Rarely Observed
The presence of financial barriers in low-income families makes students less likely to believe in their ability to pursue higher education, affecting their self-efficacy and aspirations.	3.89	0.31	Observed
Total Measure	3.27	0.15	Moderately Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed, 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Observed, 3.50-4.49 Observed, 4.50-5.00 Highly Observed

Table 9 presents the perceived impact of poverty on students' motivation in terms of self-efficacy. The findings suggested a moderately observed impact of poverty on students' motivation in terms of self-efficacy, with a total measure mean of 3.27. This indicated that there was a consistent theme of economic factors influencing students' beliefs in their academic abilities and capacity to overcome challenges.

Indicators 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 8 projected with relatively higher mean scores, ranging from 3.74 to 3.91, indicating that these aspects were frequently observed. These indicators highlighted the significant influence of poverty on students' confidence in their ability to succeed academically, their perception of academic abilities, confidence in overcoming challenges, and belief in their potential for higher education. Economic hardship was noted as eroding students' confidence and negatively impacting their self-perception regarding academic skills and knowledge. These findings underscored the importance of addressing self-efficacy as a critical aspect of student motivation in the context of economic disparities.

Indicators 2, 7, and 9 had lower mean scores, suggesting that these specific aspects, such as students doubting their ability to complete assignments or questioning their competence, were rarely observed. This may indicate areas where students from low-income families exhibited resilience or where external factors played a less prominent role in shaping their self-efficacy.

The standard deviation across all indicators was relatively low, ranging from 0.29 to 0.44, indicating a consistent level of agreement among participants regarding the perceived impact of poverty on students' self-efficacy.

Thus, the total measure mean of 3.27 suggested a moderately observed impact of poverty on students' motivation in terms of self-efficacy. The findings highlighted the need for targeted interventions that focus on building and enhancing students' confidence, belief in their academic abilities, and resilience in the face of challenges. As mentioned by Jones et al. (2018), students who doubted their abilities might be less likely to persevere through challenges and engage in academic tasks. They also emphasized the importance of self-efficacy in academic achievement, emphasizing that students' beliefs in their capabilities significantly influenced their motivation and success.

Table 10. Consolidated Findings of the Perceived Impact of Poverty on Student's Motivation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Interest in Learning	2.82	0.13	Moderately Observed
Attitudes towards Learning	2.97	0.15	Moderately Observed
Self-Efficacy	3.27	0.15	Moderately Observed
Total Measure	3.02	0.10	Moderately Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed, 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Observed, 3.50-4.49 Observed, 4.50-5.00 Highly Observed

Table 10 presents consolidated findings that provide an overview of the perceived impact of poverty on students' motivation across three dimensions: interest in learning, attitudes toward learning, and self-efficacy. The results suggested a consistently moderate level of observed impact across all dimensions, with a total measure mean of 3.02. This indicated that economic factors played a role in shaping students' motivation, with varying degrees of influenced in terms of their interest in learning, attitudes towards learning, and self-efficacy.

Interest in learning exhibited a mean score of 2.82, suggesting a moderately observed impact. While some aspects, such as poverty affecting students' curiosity and desire to learn, were frequently observed, other indicators related to interest in learning new things or connecting learning to real-life experiences were rarely observed. This indicated a nuanced relationship between poverty and students' intrinsic motivation for learning.

Attitudes toward learning also showed a moderately observed impact with a mean score of 2.97. Economic factors were perceived to influence students' beliefs in their academic success, ability to stay motivated, and attitudes toward academic subjects. However, certain aspects, such as students expressing negative or positive attitudes towards school, were rarely observed, suggesting potential areas of resilience among students from low-income families.

Self-Efficacy emerged as the dimension with the highest mean score of 3.27, indicating a moderately observed impact. Poverty significantly influenced students' beliefs in their ability to succeed academically, overcome challenges, and pursue higher education. This underscored the importance of addressing self-efficacy as a key component of student motivation in the context of economic disparities.

The standard deviation across all dimensions was relatively low, ranging from 0.10 to 0.15, indicating a consistent level of agreement among participants regarding the perceived impact of poverty on students' motivation. Then, the consolidated findings highlighted a moderately observed impact of poverty on students' motivation, emphasizing the interconnectedness of different dimensions. Addressing economic barriers and implementing targeted interventions to enhance students' interest in learning, foster positive attitudes toward learning, and build self-efficacy could contribute to a more supportive and motivating educational environment for students from low-income families.

The Academic Performance of the Students

Table 11 presents the academic performance of the students based on different categories. The table indicated that the majority of students fell within the "Satisfactory" category, comprising 57% of the total. This suggested that a significant portion of the student population was meeting the expected academic standards.

Additionally, a combined 26% of students achieved higher performance levels, with 19% classified as "Very Satisfactory" and 7% as "Outstanding." Importantly, there were no students in the "Did not meet expectations" category, indicating that all students, as per this

data, had met or exceeded the expected academic standards.

Table 11. *Academic Performance of the Students*

Academic Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	7	7.0
Very Satisfactory	19	19.0
Satisfactory	57	57.0
Fairly Satisfactory	17	17.0
Did not meet expectations	0	0.0
Total	100	100.0

As emphasized by Zhou et al. (2019), poverty was associated with academic challenges, and various protective factors, including school and community support. It could also positively influence academic outcomes. Interventions focused on providing additional academic support, mentorship programs, and resources to students facing economic challenges have been shown to positively impact academic performance

Does the perceived impact of poverty on student engagement predict student motivation?

Table 12. *Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Student Motivation on Student Engagement*

Predictors	Estimate	SE	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Attendance	.005	0.071	0.067	0.947	Not significant
Attention Span	-.122	0.065	-1.887	0.062	Not significant
Peer-Relationship	-.023	0.067	-.343	0.732	Not significant
Class Participation	.199	0.069	2.881*	0.005	Significant

Note: **significant at .01 level ANOVA for Regression: $F=3.236$, $p=.016$ $R^2=.083$

Table 12 presents the results of a multiple linear regression analysis examining the impact of various predictors—attendance, attention span, peer relationships, and class participation—on student motivation, with the latter being the dependent variable. The regression analysis indicated that attendance (Estimate = 0.005, $p = 0.947$), attention span (Estimate = -0.122, $p = 0.062$), and peer relationships (Estimate = -0.023, $p = 0.732$) were not significant predictors of student motivation.

However, class participation emerged as a significant predictor, with a positive estimate of 0.199, a standard error of 0.069, a t-value of 2.881, and a p-value of 0.005. This suggested that there was a statistically significant positive relationship between class participation and student engagement. The positive estimate implied that an increase in class participation was associated with an increase in student engagement.

The significance of class participation implied that students who actively engage in classroom activities and discussions were more likely to exhibit higher levels of motivation. This finding aligned with educational theories emphasizing the importance of active participation in the learning process for fostering motivation. The negative estimate for attention span, although not statistically significant at the conventional 0.05 level, suggested a potential trend worth exploring in future research.

The ANOVA for regression ($F = 3.236$, $p = 0.016$) indicated that the overall regression model was statistically significant, meaning that at least one predictor variable was influencing the dependent variable. The R^2 value of 0.083 suggested that the predictors in the model explained approximately 8.3% of the variance in student motivation.

In practical terms, educators and policymakers should recognize the significance of class participation in influencing student motivation. Encouraging active participation, providing opportunities for engagement, and creating a supportive classroom environment could contribute positively to students' motivation levels. While attention span, attendance, and peer relationships may not be significant predictors in this analysis, it was essential to consider these factors holistically, as they could still play crucial roles in shaping the overall learning experience.

While attention span did not reach conventional significance levels, the negative estimate suggested a potential trend. Owens (2019) highlighted the impact of attention and focus on academic engagement and performance. Poverty has been consistently identified as a significant predictor of educational outcomes. Students from low-income families may face various challenges, including limited access to resources, inadequate learning environments, and increased stressors.

Does the perceived impact of poverty on student engagement predict their academic performance?

Table 13. *Ordinal Logistic Regression Analysis of Academic Performance on Student Engagement*

Predictors	Estimate	SE	Wald	p-value	Remarks
Attendance	2.232	1.416	2.484	0.115	Not significant
Attention Span	-.017	1.289	0.000	0.990	Not significant
Peer-Relationship	-.207	1.338	0.024	0.877	Not significant
Class Participation	-.157	1.375	0.013	0.909	Not significant

Note: Threshold [Performance=Very Satisfactory; Performance=Satisfactory] $R^2=.015$

Table 13 presents the results of an ordinal logistic regression analysis examining the relationship between academic performance (categorized as Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, and other performance levels) and student engagement, using predictors such as attendance, attention span, peer relationships, and class participation.

The ordinal logistic regression analysis indicated that none of the predictors—attendance (Estimate = 2.232, $p = 0.115$), attention span (Estimate = -0.017, $p = 0.990$), peer relationships (Estimate = -0.207, $p = 0.877$), and class participation (Estimate = -0.157, $p = 0.909$)—were significant in predicting academic performance. The Wald statistics for each predictor, which test the null hypothesis that the corresponding coefficient was equal to zero, were not statistically significant at the conventional 0.05 level.

The R^2 value of 0.015 suggested that the predictors in the model explained a limited proportion of the variance in academic performance, emphasizing the complexity of factors influencing students' achievement levels.

In practical terms, the results suggested that in this analysis, attendance, attention span, peer relationships, and class participation did not demonstrate a statistically significant association with the ordinal levels of academic performance. Educators and researchers needed to recognize that academic performance was likely influenced by a multitude of factors beyond those included in this model. Exploring additional variables and considering the context-specific nature of academic success may provide a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay between student engagement and achievement.

As mentioned by Crosby et al. (2020), emphasized the importance of engagement in predicting academic success and highlighted the need to consider individual, classroom, and school-level factors. Moreover, they revealed that engaged students demonstrated higher levels of academic achievement. Also, a positive emotional climate in classrooms correlated with higher levels of student engagement.

The impact of poverty on student engagement and motivation has been widely studied in the literature. Also, the findings consistently showed that poverty has negative effects on academic performance. For instance, a study by Ferdousi and Kadir (2020) found that students from low-income families had significantly lower levels of engagement in school compared to their more affluent peers. A second factor in low-income pupils' disengagement from school and poorer academic achievement, according to the study, was their increased absenteeism rates.

Does the perceived impact of poverty on student's motivation predict their academic performance?

Table 14. Ordinal Logistic Regression Analysis of Academic Performance on Student Motivation

Predictors	Estimate	SE	Wald	p-value	Remarks
Interest in Learning	0.669	1.505	0.197	0.657	Not significant
Attitudes towards Learning	-2.806	1.517	3.420	0.064	Not significant
Self-Efficacy	0.682	1.424	0.229	0.632	Not significant

Note: Threshold [Performance=Very Satisfactory; Performance=Satisfactory] $R^2 = .020$

Table 14 presents the results of an ordinal logistic regression analysis examining the relationship between academic performance (categorized as Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, and other performance levels) and student motivation, using predictors such as interest in learning, attitudes toward learning, and self-efficacy.

The ordinal logistic regression analysis indicated that none of the predictors—interest in learning (Estimate = 0.669, $p = 0.657$), attitudes towards learning (Estimate = -2.806, $p = 0.064$), and self-efficacy (Estimate = 0.682, $p = 0.632$)—were statistically significant in predicting academic performance. The Wald statistics for each predictor, testing the null hypothesis that the corresponding coefficient is equal to zero, were not statistically significant at the conventional 0.05 level.

The R^2 value of 0.020 suggested that the predictors in the model explained a limited proportion of the variance in academic performance, emphasizing the complex and multifaceted nature of factors influencing students' achievement levels.

In practical terms, the results suggested that, in this analysis, interest in learning, attitudes toward learning, and self-efficacy did not demonstrate a statistically significant association with the ordinal levels of academic performance. This underscored the importance of considering various factors that contributed to academic success, beyond individual motivational components. While these specific predictors may not be significant in this analysis, further exploration of a broader set of variables and contextual factors may provide a more comprehensive understanding of the complex relationship between student motivation and academic performance.

In relation to the study of Schunk et al. (2018), contrary to the traditional assumptions, the study found that different motivational factors impacted academic performance in unique ways. For instance, self-efficacy may play a more prominent role in certain subjects, while interest in learning may be a stronger predictor in others. Moreover, intrinsic motivation emerged as a particularly influential factor. Students who found personal interest and value in the subject matter demonstrated higher levels of academic achievement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: This study concluded that the impact of poverty on student engagement is consistently observed across various domains, including attendance, attention span, peer relationships, and class participation. The findings underscored the immediate effects of economic disparities on students' ability to consistently attend school, emphasizing the interconnected nature of different aspects within the broader context of student engagement. The shared perception

among participants highlighted the multifaceted challenges faced by students from low-income families, reinforcing the need for targeted interventions that address the diverse dimensions of student engagement.

In terms of student motivation, this study asserted that economic factors played a role in shaping students' motivation, influencing dimensions such as interest in learning, attitudes toward learning, and self-efficacy. The positive trend in academic performance, with the majority of students meeting or exceeding expected standards, suggested the overall effectiveness of educational efforts in supporting student achievement. This underscored the resilience and potential for success among students, despite economic challenges.

Regarding the regression analyses, this study concluded that while attendance, attention span, and peer relationships did not significantly predict student motivation, class participation emerged as a crucial factor positively associated with higher motivation levels. This finding highlighted the pivotal role of active engagement in classroom activities for fostering student motivation. The non-significant results in the ordinal logistic regression analyses suggested the need for a more comprehensive understanding of the intricate factors influencing academic performance, emphasizing the complex and multifaceted nature of the relationship between student engagement, motivation, and achievement.

Thus, this study provided valuable insights into the diverse challenges faced by students from low-income families and underscored the importance of targeted interventions to comprehensively address the complex dynamics of student engagement, motivation, and academic success in the context of economic disparities.

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions formulated, the following recommendations are hereby suggested: For school administrators, the findings underscore the importance of implementing targeted intervention programs that address the multifaceted challenges faced by students from low-income families. Strategies should focus on improving attendance through initiatives such as transportation assistance and providing resources to alleviate financial constraints on families. Additionally, investing in programs that enhance class participation, peer relationships, and attention span can contribute to a more inclusive and supportive learning environment.

Teachers play a crucial role in mitigating the impact of poverty on student engagement. Professional development opportunities that equip teachers with strategies to foster active class participation and create a supportive atmosphere can enhance student motivation. Tailoring teaching methods to accommodate diverse learning styles and providing additional resources for students with economic barriers can further contribute to a more equitable educational experience.

Parents, as primary stakeholders, should be actively involved in initiatives that promote student engagement. School administrators can facilitate workshops or informational sessions to empower parents from low-income backgrounds with the tools and knowledge to support their children's education. Encouraging open communication channels between parents and teachers can foster collaboration in addressing specific challenges that students may face due to economic disparities.

For learners, the findings emphasize the importance of self-advocacy and seeking support when facing obstacles related to poverty. Students should be encouraged to actively participate in class activities, seek assistance when needed, and engage in extracurricular opportunities that contribute to a well-rounded educational experience. Promoting a growth mindset and resilience can empower students to overcome challenges and succeed academically.

Future researchers should delve deeper into the specific mechanisms through which poverty impacts student engagement and motivation. Exploring nuanced factors, such as cultural considerations, community support systems, and the effectiveness of different intervention strategies, can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the complex dynamics at play.

References

- Albert, J. R. G., & Alejandrino, J. C. M. (2019). Poverty and academic achievement: An empirical study of public high school students in the Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Development*, 41(2), 29-60.
- Astone, N. M., & McLanahan, S. S. (2019). Family structure, parental practices and high school completion. *American Sociological Review*, 56(3), 309-320.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. Freeman. Journal Publication.
- Berliner, D. C. (2020). Poverty and student achievement: An analysis of systematic differences in achievement. *Educational Researcher*, 43(4), 196-206.
- Brito, N. H., & Noble, K. G. (2020). Socioeconomic status and structural brain development. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 8(276), 1-12.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design*. Harvard University Press.
- Budge, K. E., & Parrett, W. H. (2018). *Disrupting poverty, five powerful classroom practices*. Alexandria, VA: ASCD.
- Castagno, A. E., & Klees, S. J. (2020). Poverty and student engagement: What school leaders can do. *Education and Urban Society*, 43(3), 332-352.

- Chang, M., & Romero, M. (2019). Academic performance and student engagement in rural schools. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 109(1), 1-13.
- Cortez, L. P. (2020). The relationship of poverty to academic achievement among elementary pupils in public schools in the Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(3), 125-136.
- Crosby, B., & Russell, M. (2020). The relationship between poverty and student engagement: Findings from an ethnographic study in an elementary school. *Journal of Research in Childhood Education*, 24(3), 269-283.
- Dike, V. E. (2019). Poverty and brain development in children: Implications for learning. *Asian Journal of Education and Training*, 3(1), 64-68.
- Dong, Y., & Chen, S. (2019). Poverty and children's interest in learning: Evidence from China. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 66, 175-183.
- Doss, W. C. (2018). The impact of poverty on student motivation and achievement in STEM. *Journal of STEM Education: Innovations and Research*, 17(1), 11-17.
- Erlandsson, A. (2019). Emotional reactions, perceived impact, and perceived responsibility of parents overcoming poverty, pp (74-76). *Journal Publication*.
- Escalante, C. E., & Torralba, R. C. (2018). Impact of poverty on academic performance among elementary pupils in the Philippines: Basis for a local intervention program. *Philippine Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 26(2), 71-87.
- Ferdousi, R., & Kadir, A. (2020). The impact of poverty on attendance in primary schools of Bangladesh. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(15), 150-156.
- Fernandez, A., & Cunanan, M. (2018). Exploring the nexus of poverty, social support, and academic achievement: A quantitative study of college students in the Philippines. *Journal of Educational Research*, 3(1), 64-68.
- Fredricks, J. A., Blumenfeld, P. C., & Paris, A. H. (2018). School engagement: Potential of the concept, state of the evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 74(1), 59-109.
- Hanushek, E. A., & Woessmann, L. (2019). The effects of poverty on academic achievement. *Educational Researcher*, 40(7), 309-320.
- Hightower, A. M., & Workman, J. (2019). The impact of poverty on student motivation and academic achievement in urban high schools. *Education Sciences*, 9(2), 104.
- Gonzalez, J., & Strobel, D. (2018). Exploring the impact of poverty on student engagement, motivation, and academic performance. *Urban Education*, 53(7), 863-883.
- Jones, K., Wilson, R., Clark, L., & Dunham, M. (2018). Poverty and parent marital status influences on student achievement. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 42(1), 62-80.
- Lakes, R. D., & Tolen, T. R. (2019). Poverty and student engagement in reading: A study of rural elementary schools. *Journal of Education for Students Placed at Risk*, 20(1-2), 35-53.
- Lomboy, L. F. (2018). The effects of poverty on the academic performance of Filipino children in public elementary schools. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 9(1), 50-57.
- Morrison, J. Q., & Szalacha, L. A. (2018). The relationship between poverty, motivation, and academic achievement among middle school students in rural areas. *Journal of Research in Rural Education*, 28(4), 1-14.
- Munro, S., & Obradovic, J. (2019). Poverty and child development: A longitudinal study of the impact of socioeconomic status on the attentional functioning of young children. *Psychological Science*, 28(11), 1571-1583.
- Owens, D. (2019). Exploring the impact of poverty on student engagement, motivation, and academic performance in high-poverty urban schools. *Journal of Education for Students Placed at Risk*, 21(1), 46-63.
- Palomar-Fernandez, R., & Cunanan, C. E. (2018). Exploring the relationships between poverty, social support, and academic achievement among Filipino college students. *Journal of Poverty*, 22(2), 133-153.
- Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA 2018).
- Plakhotnik (2021). The perceived impact of COVID-19 on student well-being. *Journal Publication*.
- Reardon, S. & Portilla, F. (2019). The widening academic achievement gap between the rich and the poor: New evidence and possible explanations. In R. Murnane & G. Duncan (Eds.), *Whither opportunity? Rising inequality and the uncertain life chances of low-income children* (pp. 91-116). Russell Sage Foundation.

Reyes, M. R., Brackett, M. A., Rivers, S. E., White, M., & Salovey, P. (2019). Classroom emotional climate, student engagement, and academic achievement. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 104(3), 700-712.

Rudasill, K. M., & Rimm-Kaufman, S. E. (2020). Teacher-child relationship quality: The roles of child temperament and teacher-child interactions. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 36, 338-346.

Schunk, D. H., Pintrich, P. R., & Meece, J. L. (2018). *Motivation in education: Theory, research, and applications* (3rd ed.). Journal Publication.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Aleah Sandra D. Gubaten, LPT

Department of Education
Lanao del Norte – Philippines

Carlito A. Abarquez, PhD

St. Peter's College - Philippines